

Teacher Indifference Rejection as a Predictor of Emotional Unresponsiveness School Children

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the impact of teacher indifference rejection on students' emotional unresponsiveness and investigates the relationship between teacher control behavior and student dependency using regression analysis. Emotional- unresponsiveness refers to a lack of emotional reaction or engagement from students, often manifesting as disengagement, apathy, or a lack of participation in classroom activities. The hypothesis posits that teacher indifference significantly influences this emotional detachment in the classroom setting. Data was collected from a sample of high school students and their teachers through structured questionnaires. Emotional unresponsiveness among students was measured alongside perceived teacher indifference. Additionally, the study explored how varying levels of teacher control behavior affect student dependency. Regression analysis results implied that teacher indifference is a significant predictor of students' emotional unresponsiveness, as evidenced by the model's F-value of 23.874, t-value of 4.886, standardized beta (β) coefficient of 0.170, and a significance level (P) of 0.00. These findings suggest that students are more likely to become emotionally detached when they perceive their teachers as indifferent. Conversely, the analysis of teacher control behavior showed that it was not a significant predictor of student dependency, with a standardized beta (β) coefficient of 0.067, t-value of 1.504, and significance level (P) of 0.133. These findings underscore the critical role of teacher engagement in fostering emotional responsiveness among students, while also indicating that control behaviors alone do not significantly influence student dependency. Implications for educational practices and teacher training programs are discussed, emphasizing the need for fostering supportive and interactive classroom environments to mitigate emotional unresponsiveness among students.

Keywords: Teacher Indifference, Rejection as a Predictor, Emotional Unresponsiveness, School Children,

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1. Introduction

Schools significantly impact students' psychological health and academic, physical, social, emotional, and moral growth. This is all done to help people reach their full potential and lead fulfilling lives. Moreover, student association with teachers and schools developed senses of warmth, emotional responsiveness, problem-solving skills, pro-social behavior the positive transition from one stage to another (Sarfaraz et al, 2022; Weare,2015).

According to the Teacher Acceptance-rejection Theory (TARQ), Teachers play a crucial role as attachment figures for their students, and rejection conduct on their part may exacerbate psychological maladjustment of students. Moreover, contemporary studies indicates that Schools have been described as a reflection of society, and educators play a crucial role in imparting social standards about prosocial behavior (Bergin & Bergin, 2009; Kuyumuc et al., 2018; Yildirim & Erkman, 2008).The fundamental tenet of the theory is that, as humans have evolved, they have acquired a persistent, physiologically grounded emotional desire for affirmative responses from the people who matter most to them (Ahmed, Khalique, & Rohner (2012); Rohner (2010); Ali, Rohner, & Carrasco, 2015).As stated by Rohner (2004) to the Perceived Teacher Acceptance-Rejection Theory (TARQ), interpersonal acceptance and rejection are capable of accurately predicting how well children and adults will transition psychologically and behaviorally across a range of sociodemographic categories and cultural contexts.

Although Rohner, Khalique, and Cournoyer (2005) suggested that whenever people's needs are not met, they feel rejected by important people (parents, friends, and teachers), and this rejection causes personality outcomes like emotional insensitivity, dependence, low self-esteem, low self-adequacy, negative worldview, and hostility and aggression. Emotional unresponsiveness is a person's inability to express themselves freely and openly their emotions whereas dependence is an internal, psychologically felt wish or yearning for emotional support, care, comfort, attention, nurturance, and similar responses from significant others (Rohner,2022).Therefore, this article aims to examine whether teacher indifference rejection predicts emotional unresponsiveness in students and to predict the relationship between perceived teacher control behavior and student dependency.

Earlier study in Pakistan suggested that the emotional well-being of students improves when they are acknowledged and appreciated by their teachers. Moreover, this promotes love, fairness, purpose in life, and psychological well-being, all of which contribute to healthy stress management in the classroom (Sarfaraz, Malik, & Nadeem, 2024).Additionally Schools can play a significant role in teaching social and emotional parts of the world education system have adopted now interventions to endorsement to well-being needs of school children recommended by the World Health Organization in (2014).

“In general, ... rejected children tend to be fearful, insecure, attention-seeking, jealous, hostile, and lonely. Many of these children have difficulty in later life expressing and responding to affection. Probably all conditions of rejection are conducive to self-devaluation and to an evaluation of the world as an insecure and dangerous place, thus inhibiting normal spontaneity and the confident reality testing essential for normal development” (Rohner, 2021, p. 43).”

Figure 1: Depicted Certain of the severely rejected children's negative views of themselves

Research finding shows that documented by (Courtois, 2004) compared rejected and neglected group of children with the accepted children found that rejected children are distinguished from their accepted classmates and are described by their teacher's aggressive and emotional unresponsiveness. The violent disciplinary measures in schools are consequence of school runaway and result in several physical and psychological disturbance among the thousands of children (Deeba, 2009). Furthermore, Some consequences of perceived rejection are also found in developmental trauma and posttraumatic stress disorders. These results provide an important link in helping understand the heightened emotional sensitivity of many adults who had been rejected as children. These and other neurobiological and neuropsychological changes may compromise children's central nervous system and psychosocial development (Ford, 2005; Courtois, 2004).

Fig 2 shows the brain scans of the two children are compared in Fig. 2: generally growing brain: exhibits strong activity and vivid hues (red, orange, yellow, and green), which point to normal, healthy brain development and function as well as active, well-developed temporal lobes. On the other hand the development of a child's brain during abuse, trauma, and neglect: exhibits decreased activity in the darker hues (green, blue, and black), which suggests inferior brain development and function. The temporal lobes are particularly undeveloped and less active (Daye & Slikkers 2018).

Figure 2: Adopted by Slikkers & Daye (2018)

2. Method

2.1 Procedure

This study's participants were recruited by the convenience sampling technique. One nonprobability selection technique called convenience sampling allows researchers to choose subjects for focused study who are simple to locate (Kuyumcu ,2020). This study involved 500 high school students who were residents of Hyderabad. There were 250 pupils (50%) who were male and 250 students (50%) who were female. Student ages ranged from 10 to 18 years old (mean age = 13.4, standard deviation = 1.13). Participation in this study was restricted to students who had both adolescent and parental consent. They filled out the required forms during scheduled class meetings. Throughout the data gathering phase, the study's researcher remained within the classroom. The Institutional Review Board (IRB) mandated that the researcher disclose to participants the nature of the study, as well as the anonymity and confidentiality of their answers, before they may respond. Each participant filled out the self-report questions in Urdu, which are explained below. It took roughly 50 minutes to complete this operation.

2.2 Measures

Teacher's acceptance-rejection questionnaire-child version short form

This measure was developed by Rohner (2005) to estimate the perception of teacher rejection levels. The questionnaire contains 24 items. The measure consists of four scales: (1) Warmth/Affection (e.g. My teachers say nice things about me), (2) Hostility/Aggression (My teachers hit me, even when I do not deserve it), (3) Indifference/Neglect (My teachers' pay no attention to me), and (4) Undifferentiated rejection (My teachers seem to dislike me). The TARQ is scored on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = almost never true to 4 = almost always true. The sum of scores can range from 24 to 96. As commonly used worldwide, total scores were used in this study. A high total score shows a low perception of teacher acceptance of students.

The alpha reliability coefficient of this scale is ($r=.80$) which indicates that it is a highly reliable scale (Rohner et al., 2010).

Personality assessment questionnaire-child version (PAQ)

This measure was developed to estimate the level of psychological maladjustment (Rohner ,2005). It consists of 42 items, six items for each of seven scales containing (a) Hostility/Aggression (e.g. I want to hit something or someone), (b) Dependence (I like my parents to make a fuss over me when I am hurt or sick), (c) Negative Self-Esteem (I get unhappy with myself), (d) Negative Self-Adequacy I think I am a failure), (e) Emotional Unresponsiveness (I have difficulty showing people how

I feel), (f) Emotional Instability (I am in a bad mood and grumpy without any good reason), and (g) Negative Worldview (For me the World is unhappy place). The PAQ is scored on a 4-point Likert-type scale, with 1 (almost never true), 2 (rarely true), 3 (sometimes true), and 4 (almost always true). The sum of scores can spread from 42 to

168. A high total score means a low level of psychological adjustment of an individual. As commonly used worldwide, total scores obtained via the PAQ were employed in this study. Scores at or above 105 suggest significant psychological maladjustment. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the original form of the PAQ is .84. Extensive evidence reported in Rohner and Khaleque (2005) shows the measure to be reliable and valid for research in the United States and cross-culturally.

2.3 Personal Information Form

The PIF is a short questionnaire designed to collect demographic information related to gender, age, class, grades, mother tongue, parental education and occupation.

3. Results

Table 1 shows the mean score for the TARQ is 67.48, with a standard deviation of 11.58. This suggests a moderate level of perceived acceptance and rejection among the students. Moreover, the relatively high standard deviation indicates variability in students' perceptions of teacher behavior. Furthermore, the mean score of 10.69 and standard deviation of 3.83 for the Indifference/Negligence subscale indicate that students experience varying levels of indifference or negligence from their teachers. Whereas the mean PAQ score is 90.14 with a low standard deviation of 2.21, suggesting that student's personalities adjustment with minor deviations. The mean score of 13.22 and standard deviation of 3.03 for emotional unresponsiveness indicate moderate levels of emotional unresponsiveness among students, with some variation.

Table 1: Mean, Standard Deviation of Teacher Acceptance-rejection questionnaire, Personality assessment questionnaire and their Subscales

Scales	n	Mean	Standard Deviation
TARQ	500	67.48	11.58
Indifference/Negligence	500	10.69	3.83
Personality assessment questionnaire	500	90.14	2.21
Emotional unresponsiveness	500	13.22	3.03

Table shows the regression model, student emotional unresponsiveness is significantly predicted by teacher indifference rejection ($F = 23.874$, $P = .000$). It is evident from the high p-value and strong F-value that the model is statistically sound. Likewise, the regression's average of the squares (210.660) in relation to the total (4604.912) indicates that the model accounts for a significant portion of the variation in students' emotional unresponsiveness. In accordance with 170), students' emotional unresponsiveness increases by 170 units for each increase in perceived teacher indifference. This is a significant rise, suggesting that teacher behaviour students' emotions.

The standardized coefficient (Beta) of .214 indicates a moderate effect size. This suggests that teacher indifference is a moderately strong predictor of student emotional unresponsiveness. The t-value of 4.88 and p-value of .000 reinforce the statistical

significance of teacher indifference as a predictor of emotional unresponsiveness. This strong t-value indicates that the relationship is not due to chance.

Table 2: Regression Analysis of Teacher Indifference rejection and Student Emotional-Unresponsiveness

	Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P
1	Regression	210.660	1	210.660	23.874	.000
	Residual	4394.252	498	8.824		
	Total	4604.912	499			

Table 3: Beta Weights of Predictor Variables in the Model

	Standardized		Unstandardized Coefficients		
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta	t	P
	11.40	.395		28.89	.000
	.170	.035	.214	4.88	.000

*p<.05

Table 3: indicating that teacher indifference rejection ($F = 23.874$), ($t = 4.886$), ($\beta = 0.170$), ($P = 0.00$) is significant predictor of student emotional- unresponsiveness.

4. Discussion

In this study we examined the relationship between the perceived teacher acceptance-rejection and emotional well-being of school children. The statistical analysis reveals that teacher indifference and rejection are significant predictors of student emotional unresponsiveness. Perceived teacher rejection is the most common problem of most of the students in our society. Neuro- Psychology indicated that rejection from powerful person on children live tends to disrupt early brain growth associated with learning and memory hinder functioning of the nervous system and it's also continued throughout life span (Rohner, 2017). Children are silent by their teacher who makes them an easy target to express their aggression and frustration. Thus, these findings suggested continuous effort to support students to encourage perceived teacher acceptance beneficial to counter behavioral problem of school children. Perceived rejection is typically present prior to the start of many mental health concerns, such as depression and depressed affect, conduct issues and behavior disorders, and substance abuse, as per longitudinal evidence published (Rohner and Britner 2002; Gershoff, 2002). Recent research supports these findings, emphasizing the critical role of teacher student relationships in fostering a supportive educational environment and promoting positive emotional and academic outcomes for students (Lapidot-Lefler & Israeli, 2024). Moreover, Research has shown that fostering positive teacher-student relationships is highly beneficial for both teachers and students. By

nurturing these relationships, teachers can create a more supportive and effective learning environment, enhancing educational outcomes and overall well-being (Wang et al., 2024). In addition, with interpersonal skills serving as a moderator, good relationships between educators and students have a significant positive impact on students' enjoyment of learning and lower levels of stress. This demonstrates that teachers' ability to effectively manage and deal with their emotions can mitigate the negative effects that students may experience when they witness their indifference (Shang & Xie, 2023). Overall, these contemporary studies highlight the profound impact of teacher behaviors on student emotional and academic outcomes, reinforcing the need for teacher training programs to focus on building positive, supportive relationships with students to foster a healthy educational environment (Al-Yagon & Mikulincer, 2006; Rohner, Khaleque, Elias, & Sultana, 2010; Ali, Khaleque, & Rohner, 2015; Ahmed, Khaleque, & Rohner, 2012; Rohner, 2010; Ali, Rohner, & Carrasco, 2015).

5. Conclusion

Teacher indifference or rejection is a significant predictor of student emotional unresponsiveness. This relationship is statistically significant and suggests that higher levels of perceived indifference or rejection from teachers are associated with increased emotional unresponsiveness in students. Perceived rejection is often linked to mental health issues like depression, depressed affect, conduct issues, behavior disorders, and substance abuse. Research indicates a reciprocal and bidirectional association between children's behavioral problems and their perception of rejection, highlighting the importance of understanding and addressing these issues (Rohner & Britner, 2002; Gershoff, 2002).

Ethical Approval and Consent to Participate.

The participants provided their written informed consent to participate in this study. Moreover, the participants were reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the Psychology Department of Psychology University, of Karachi, Pakistan. Availability of supporting data - The datasets processed and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding/first author on reasonable request

5. References

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